

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B302
Date: 28 June 2007
Take Off: 11:05:48
Landing: 15:47:30
Flight Time: 4h 41m 42s

Campaign: GERBIL

Operating Area: Nouakchott -> Niamey

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM1	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	Core Chem.	Kate Turnbull	FAAM
5	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM
6	Mission Scientist 1	Jim Haywood	Met Office
7	Mission Scientist 2	Ben Johnson	Met Office
8	AVAPS	Doug Anderson	FAAM
9	Filters	Paula Formenti	University of Paris 12 (LISA)
10	ARIES	Stuart Rogers	Met Office
11	CCM2	Jackie Mulholland	Directflight
12	Neph / PSAP / SWS	Andy Wilson	Met Office
13	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
14	Mission Scientist 3	John Marsham	Leeds University
15	transit	Steve Ball	FAAM
16	transit	Jamie Trembath	FAAM

Flight Track:

B302 Track 28-JUN-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B302
 Date: 28 June 2007
 Project: Gerbil
 Location: Niamey - Marrakesh

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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093619		DRS	0.03 kft	085	recording B302
104010		video	0.02 kft	085	#1 aft, #2 up (for pirouette)
105512		wow	0.02 kft	085	set
105528		inu	0.02 kft	085	to navigate
105543		cgps	0.02 kft	085	B302cgps.log
105604		gin	0.02 kft	084	on
110052	110332	pirouette	0.02 kft	037	045M
110149		video	0.02 kft	266	recording
110345		ASP	0.02 kft	037	open
110358		psap	0.02 kft	036	flow on
110548		T/O	0.02 kft	219	Nouakchott
110611	112349	Profile 1	0.41 - 17.0 kft	219	start at T/O
110627		heimann	0.60 kft	219	open
110701		video	1.00 kft	219	#2 reset to down after T/O
112349	113625	Run 1.1	17.0 kft	095	
112707		Sonde 1	17.0 kft	094	
113625	115356	Profile 2	17.0 - 2.0 kft	097	
113649		bbr	16.7 kft	099	extend
114020		bbr	13.2 kft	085	upper reset
114500		heimann	9.3 kft	084	cal 14
115356	134620	Run 2.1	2.0 - 2.1 kft	086	
115413		bbr	2.1 kft	085	retract
122945		fm	2.1 kft	085	pc crash & reboot
123807		Video	2.1 kft	086	#3 aft, #4 down
131155		psap	2.1 kft	086	filter change 1 > 2
134621	140238	Profile 3	2.1 - 19.0 kft	104	
134710		bbr	3.0 kft	120	extend
134728		heimann	3.2 kft	125	cal 14
140239	140856	Run 3.1	19.0 kft	116	
140303		bbr	19.0 kft	117	retract
140857	141854	Profile 4	19.0 - 9.0 kft	117	
140922		bbr	18.7 kft	117	extend
141110		Video	17.0 kft	118	#5 aft, #6 down start
141855	144737	Run 4.1	9.0 kft	120	
141929		bbr	9.0 kft	119	retract
144737	145806	Profile 5	9.0 - 19.0 kft	119	
144759		bbr	9.3 kft	120	extend
145807	150756	Run 5.1	19.0 kft	122	
145839		bbr	19.0 kft	126	retract
150757	152638	Profile 6	19.0 - 3.2 kft	124	
150824		bbr extend	18.6 kft	125	
152310		Video	6.1 kft	121	#7 aft, #8 down start
152638	154255	Run 6.1	3.2 kft	124	
152702		bbr	3.1 kft	124	retract
154256	154315	Profile 7	3.2 - 3.0 kft	199	at land
154514		bbr	2.4 kft	242	extend
154712		heimann	0.97 kft	264	closed
154730		Land	0.81 kft	265	Niamey
155255		ASP	0.84 kft	103	closed

B302 Track 28-JUN-07

FAAM Sortie Brief (provisional #2 as at 16:00Z, 26th June 2007)

Gerbils: Geostationary Earth Radiation Budget Intercomparison of Longwave and Shortwave radiation.

Flight No: B302

Date: 28th June 2007

Trial objectives:

To carry out in-situ and remote sensing measurements of Saharan dust and the associated effect on solar and terrestrial radiation.

Location:

Over land areas between Nouakchott (Mauritania) and Niamey (Niger) along the 18N line of latitude.

Weather:

High loadings of dust aerosols. Clear skies preferred.

Special requirements:

TERRA: MISR overpass at Nouakchott at 11:38Z

Instruments of particular importance:

Nephelometer/wet-nephelometer combination

PCASP

PSAP

BBRs

SWS/SHIMS

ARIES

Flight pattern:

1. If clear from cloud, perform a 'pirouette' manoeuvre taking ~3minutes for a 360 turn.
2. Take off from Nouakchott at 11:00Z.
3. FROM TAKEOFF perform a SLR at MPA towards the east along 18°N until 18°N, 7°W (180mins, T=180mins).
4. Turn towards Niamey and then make a profile ascent to FL210 (or above the dust layer) (80mins, T=260mins).
5. Profile descent to landing at Niamey (20mins, T=280mins).
6. If free from cloud perform a pirouette on landing.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.302** Date 28 June 07 Name Jim Haywood Page 1 of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Microtops suggests AOD = 0.68.
					Dusty.
					A little v. thin Ci at 10:45 - check with microtops.
					Start pirouette. SWS making orbit measurements
					No cloud visible above.
					End pirouette.
~11:05	PI↑	0ft			Start profile at 0 ft.
					Clear from dust at surface.
					Dusty at 3000ft.
11:22					Free from cloud ahead & above.
11:23:49	End PI SFR1	FL170 →			Just above dust.
					AOD estimate = 0.6 from integration & 1.5 'bodge' factor.
11:27:07					Launch solar #1.
					FL170
					r=g=b. Scat
					50ft
					50. x10 ^{-450m⁻¹}

VISUAL / NO LAPTOP

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B**.....302..... Date 28 June 07 Name Jim Haywood Page 2..... of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:36:25	End R1 S+P2	FL170 ↓			Descend into the dust layer from just in the top. Upper pygeometers reset at 11:37 (ish).
11:17					PCASP voltage < 6V.
	End PZ/S+RZ	FL25			QNH = 1029 mb. 1800 ft AGL.
11:56					Interesting surface features. until 1200Z. Escarpments etc. Photos taken here.
12:05					Rocky mini-mountains with orange sand. Some scrub.
12:15					Rocky features decreasing more orange sand. Neph increasing from $\sim 70 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$ at 13W to $150 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$ at 10.5W
12:25					Becoming more turbulent Heiman $T_s \sim 47C$
12:33:8					Visibility much improved

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B**.....302..... Date 28 June 07..... Name Jim Hayward..... Page 3..... of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:36					Surface character changed completely - sand dunes that are orange with white sand in the lee of them.
12:40					Very good vis now > 20 miles
12:50					Continued good vis Neph ~ 35m ⁻¹ . Discontinuity in neph around 10V, with different size particles to the west/east of this point. Seems clear from cloud above.
13:00					Rock escarpment to the LHS. Some more black rocks here.
13:09					Neph scattering increasing to ~ 200m ⁻¹ .
13:30					PCASP Volts = 5.80 Noise in channel 1.
13:35					13:35 5042'W → brighter surface reflectance here. More white sand.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B**.....302..... Date 28/06/07..... Name Jim Haywood..... Page 4 of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
13:38					Upper BBRs show very little influence of cloud. Perhaps a few Ci patches around 13:22 & 13:30.
13:46:21	<u>End R2</u> <u>P3</u>	FL25		18°5W	Start profile ascent Top of dust layer at FL170.
14:02:39	<u>End P3</u> <u>St R3.1</u>				Some patches of Ci above.
14:08:57	<u>End R3.1</u> <u>St P4</u>				Descend to FL90.
14:18:55	<u>End P4</u> <u>St R3.2</u>	FL90 →			
14:47:47	<u>End R4</u> <u>St P5</u>	FL90 ↑			
14:54:50					Top of dust at FL170

Supplemental log from mission 2
Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.302** Date 28/6/07 Name Ben Johnson Page 1 of 3

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Microtops $\tau_{550} \sim 0.6$
					Few tiny wisps of cirrus but probably any cloud really should be fine for radiation measurements
					T=28°C. light westerly (5 KTs)
					Tdew = 19°C. Reasonably hazy.
1030	SWS				doing scanning run before aircraft moves away from stand. AIRES also looking up
1100	Pirouettes				with SWS pointing SZA +10°.
1100					SZA = 30°
1105148	T/O			NOUAKCHOTT	
110611	P1	sfc			$\tau_{aerosol} = 0.4$
112349		FL170			Just stepped short of
112707	Sender	"			dust layer top to
112349	R1.1	"			allow a run at just
113625	End	"			about over top of dust layer
113625	P2	FL170			we are cloud free
				pyranometer upper	is look stable. (no cirrus influence)
1138					MISR overpass
1145		FL100			Green scattering sometimes exceeding red & blue.
115356	End	2000ft		18N 12.7W	
115356	R2.1	2000ft			1800ft AGL SWS
1154-1210		"		12.7W	Going over very interesting surface albedos varying from 0.2-0.45
					scenery, dark rocks, valleys 'waddy' few villages. Few scribbly trees/bushes

$\bar{AB} = 90$ miles. Aim for AB to be centred on overpass unless cloudy there. $\Rightarrow$ A = 15.3 w, B = 13.7 w

$$\begin{array}{l}
 18 \text{ mins} \\
 \times 4.5 \\
 \hline
 = 81 \text{ miles}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 5 \text{ mins} \\
 \times 5 \\
 \hline
 = 25 \text{ miles}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 18 \text{ mins} \\
 \times 4.5 \\
 \hline
 = 81 \text{ miles}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{r}
 \text{Total} = 81 \\
 81 \\
 25 \\
 \hline
 187
 \end{array}$$

~ MISR swath.

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 302

Date: 28/6/07	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 10:00:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
11:06:00																Start Profile 1 from takeoff	
11:08:00	250	0.09	4	30	5											FL020	
11:08:55	310	0.09		40	4											FL030	
11:09:54	305	0.09	5	50	5											FL040	
11:10:50	170	0.09		20	3											FL050	
11:11:52	190	0.09		20	3											FL060	
11:13:00	190	0.09		10	3											FL070	
11:14:24	140	0.08		10	3											FL080	
11:15:20	115	0.09	6	20	3											FL090	
11:16:33	110	0.09		15	3											FL100	
11:17:45	125	0.10		15	3											FL110	
11:18:57	145	0.10		15	2											FL120	
11:19:50	160	0.09		15	1											FL130	
11:20:45	160	0.09		20	2											FL140	
11:21:41	190	0.09		20	2											FL150	
11:22:48	180	0.07		10	2											FL160	
11:23:48																End of P1 & Start Run 1.1 @ FL170	
11:24:00	150	0.06		5												Ch1 noise , PCASP heater on	
11:26:00	Noise		7	5													
11:28:00	Noise			5													
11:30:00	Noise			5													
11:32:00	Noise			3													
11:34:00	Noise			3													
11:36:25																End of Run 1.1 & Start P2 from FL170	
11:37:34	Noise			15	1											FL160	
11:38:21	Noise			15	2											FL150	
11:39:26	Noise			15	2											FL140	
11:40:28	Noise			20	1											FL130	
11:41:32	Noise			20	2											FL120	
11:42:53	Noise			20	2											FL110	
11:44:08	Noise			30	5											FL100	
11:45:28	Noise			30	3											FL090	
11:46:34	Noise		8	15	2											FL080	
11:47:40	Noise			20	3											FL070	
11:48:40	Noise			15	3											FL060	
11:49:45	Noise			50	3											FL050	
11:50:54	Noise		9	70	7											FL040	
11:52:15	Noise		10	70	6											FL030	
11:53:55																End of P2 & Start Run 2.1 @ FL020	
11:54:00	Noise		Fail														
11:56:00	150	0.06	0	50	3												
11:58:00	140	0.10		30	3												
12:00:00	150	0.10	Fail	30	3												
12:04:00	150	0.10	0	30	3												
12:06:00	170	0.10		30	2												
12:08:00	170	0.09		30	2												

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 302

Date: 28/6/07	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 10:00:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
12:10:00	170	0.09	1238	30	3												
12:12:00	170	0.09		30	3												
12:14:00	180	0.10		30	3												
12:16:00	190	0.10	Reset	40	5												
12:18:00	200	0.10	0	50	8												
12:20:00	190	0.10		60	3												
12:22:00	200	0.10		60	3												
12:24:00	220	0.10		60	3												
12:26:00	240	0.10		70	1												
12:28:00	220	0.10		80	3												
12:30:00	230	0.11		80	3												
12:32:00	200	0.10		70	3												
12:34:00	110	0.09		10	1												
12:36:00	110	0.09		10	1												
12:38:00	110	0.08		10	1												
12:40:00	100	0.08		10	1												
12:42:00	90	0.08		10	2												
12:44:00	100	0.08		10	2												
12:46:00	90	0.08		10	2												
12:48:00	100	0.09		10	1												
12:50:00	100	0.09		15	2												
12:52:00	90	0.09	1	15	2												
12:54:00	105	0.10		15	2												
12:56:00	100	0.10		20	2												
12:58:00	125	0.10		30	3												
13:00:00	160	0.10		70	4	2	200										
13:02:00	150	0.11		50	3												
13:04:00	145	0.11		50	4	1											
13:06:00	160	0.11	2	70	5	5	200										
13:08:00	245	0.10		80	8												
13:10:00	215	0.11		80	5												
13:12:00	210	0.11		80	4	1	300										
13:14:00	210	0.10		70	3	1	300										
13:16:00	210	0.10		70	3	1	400										
13:18:00	210	0.11		80	2												
13:20:00	210	0.11		70	5												
13:22:00	220	0.11		70	5												
13:24:00	210	0.11		80	5												
13:26:00	210	0.10		70	3												
13:28:00	190	0.11		60	3												
13:30:00	160	0.11		50	3												
13:32:00	140	0.10		40	3												
13:34:00	105	0.10	3	20	3												
13:36:00	100	0.10	4	15	2												
13:38:00	110	0.10		20	3												
13:40:00	120	0.10	5	20	2												

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 302

Date: 28/6/07	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 10:00:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 3 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
13:42:00	110	0.10	5	20	2												
13:44:00	120	0.11		15	1												
13:46:19																End of Run 2.1 & Start P3	
13:47:22	150	0.09		15												FL030	
13:48:20	100	0.09		15	1											FL040	
13:49:11	110	0.10		15	3											FL050	
13:50:04	125	0.10		15	1											FL060	
13:51:59	90	0.09		15	1											FL070	
13:51:56	105	0.09		15	1											FL080	
13:52:48	95	0.09		15	1											FL090	
13:53:49	70	0.10	6	10	1											FL100	
13:54:40	73	0.10		10												FL110	
13:55:45	75	0.10		10												FL120	
13:56:40	90	0.10		10												FL130	
13:57:44	100	0.09		10												FL140	
13:58:38	100	0.08														FL150	
13:59:50	100	0.08	Fail	10	1											FL160	
14:01:45	20	0.06	0		1											FL180	
14:02:38																End of P3 & Start Run 3.1 @ FL190	
14:03:00	Noise															PCASP heater on	
14:05:00	Noise																
14:07:00	Noise																
14:08:55																End of Run 3.1 & Start Run 4 from FL190	
14:10:12	Noise															FL180	
14:11:10	Noise			10	2											FL170	
14:12:19	Noise			20	2											FL160	
14:13:05	Noise			20	3											FL150	
14:14:02	Noise			50	2											FL140	
14:15:01	Noise			60	2											FL130	
14:15:55	Noise			60	2											FL120	
14:17:00	Noise			60	5											FL110	
14:17:56	Noise		1	70	5											FL100	
14:18:53																End of P4 & Start Run 4.1 @ FL110	
14:19:00	Noise		1	70	3												
14:21:00	Noise			60	3												
14:23:00	Noise		2	70	3												
14:25:00	Noise		3	60	3												
14:27:00	Noise			60	3												
14:29:00	Noise			60	3												
14:31:00	Noise		4	60	3												
14:33:00	Noise			10	2												
14:35:00	Noise			15	3												
14:37:00	Noise			15	3												
14:39:00	Noise			20	3												
14:41:00	Noise			20	3												
14:43:00	Noise			30	3												

FAAM Dropsonde Flight Log

Flight No.	B302	Date	28 Jun 2007	Operator	Doug Anderson	Page No.	1 of 1
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GMT	Sonde No.	Event <i>eg land, splashdown</i>	Comments <i>pressure hPa, T deg C, RH %, wind direction deg, wind speed m/s, longitude, latitude, height m</i>
11:27:09	1	Launch	526.60 -6.80 41.58 116.10 15.00 -14.60 -14.684400 17.928800 5190.10
11:33:47	1	Land	1005.69 30.35 999.00 259.21 3.63 -12.11 -14.702927 17.927602 -264.27

Filter Sampling Log

Flight No:

B302

Date:

28 JUN 2007

Operator:

Type of filters mounted in	Top inlet	47 mm Nuclepore (0.4 µm pore size)	Bottom inlet	47 mm Nuclepore (0.4 µm pore size)
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Run No	Disk #1 TOP	Disk #2 MIDDLE	Disk #3 BOTTOM	Inlet Top/ Bottom	Time On	Time Off	Flight Run	Accum Vol [l]	Comments
Filters run1	235-07	----	----	Bottom	11:53:56	12:33:00	R2.1	1572	R2.1, 2.1 kfeet, sigma_scatt ~90 Mm-1
Filters run1	236-07	----	----	Top	11:53:56	12:33:00	R2.1	2175	
Filters run 2	239-07	----	----	Bottom	12:37:00	13:08:00	R2.1	1176	R2.1, 2.1 kfeet
Filters run 2	242-07	----	----	Top	12:37:00	13:08:00	R2.1	1624	
Filters run 3	237-07	----	----	Bottom	13:11:00	13:46:21	R2.1	1359	R2.1, 2.1 kfeet, sigma_scatt ~120 Mm-1, sigma_scatt ~50 Mm-1 @ end of run
Filters run 3	240-07	----	----	Top	13:11:00	13:46:21	R2.1	1876	
Filters run 4	241-07	----	----	Bottom	14:18:55	14:47:37	R4.1	1076	R4.1, FL090, sigma_scatt ~90 Mm-1
Filters run 4	238-07	----	----	Top	14:18:55	14:47:37	R4.1	1612	

B302_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

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09:39:35.28 --- - - - -
09:39:35.28 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
09:39:35.28 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
                                tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
09:39:35.28 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B302
09:39:35.28 --- - - - -
09:39:52.82 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
09:40:30.48 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
09:40:38.59 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
09:41:19.81 --- - - - - *** Flight B302 Nouakchott to Niamey
09:41:26.90 --- - - - - *** preflight testing
09:41:34.52 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:41:40.90 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:41:47.42 SWS - - 200 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 200ms.
09:41:50.19 SWS - - - 750 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 750ms.
09:41:53.01 USH - - 500 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 500ms.
09:41:55.76 USH - - - 250 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 250ms.
09:41:58.76 USH - - - 500 NIR int.time changed from 250ms to 500ms.
09:42:01.80 USH - - 350 - VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 350ms.
09:42:05.88 LSH - - 300 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 300ms.
09:42:08.84 LSH - - - 400 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 400ms.
09:42:13.00 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:42:13.00 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:42:13.01 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:42:18.19 USH - - 200 - VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 200ms.
09:42:22.61 USH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
09:42:26.18 SWS - - 500 - VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 500ms.
09:42:31.83 LSH - - 750 - VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 750ms.
09:42:34.41 LSH - - - 750 NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
09:42:36.69 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:42:36.76 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:42:37.46 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:42:42.33 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:42:44.63 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:42:45.40 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:42:49.47 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:42:49.49 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:42:49.86 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:42:55.30 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:42:57.40 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:42:57.61 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:43:00.13 SWS - - - - Idling
09:43:01.25 USH - - - - Idling
09:43:04.56 LSH - - - - Idling
09:43:19.76 --- - - - - *** preflight OK all to idle.
10:27:23.41 --- - - - - *** on ground scanning run before take off
10:27:56.75 --- - - - - *** cloud free above. Aircraft stationary on
                                headin 85Deg
10:28:11.57 --- - - - - *** AC heading 85 deg
10:28:35.93 --- - - - - *** Solar azimuth 75.1 degrees
10:28:46.70 --- - - - - *** approx 30 deg per scan
10:29:13.31 --- - - - - *** solar zenith 37.34 deg
10:29:18.87 --- - - - - *** starting gata
10:29:21.47 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:29:21.47 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:29:21.48 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:29:24.39 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:29:24.55 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:29:24.69 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:29:29.25 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
10:29:30.23 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:29:32.32 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:29:32.53 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:29:37.20 SWS - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 100ms.
10:29:41.01 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:29:43.68 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:29:46.56 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.

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10:29:48.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:29:49.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:29:54.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:30:09.56	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws 50Aft
10:30:39.80	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws to 50 Fore
10:30:47.44	SWS	-	-	25	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 25ms.
10:30:50.67	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 100ms.
10:30:55.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:30:56.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:31:30.95	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws to 40 AFT
10:31:41.25	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 25ms to 100ms.
10:31:43.58	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 300ms.
10:31:46.26	SWS	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 400ms.
10:31:48.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:31:52.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:32:26.45	---	-	-	-	-	*** SWS to 40 FORE
10:32:34.23	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 10ms.
10:32:38.79	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 50ms.
10:32:42.05	SWS	-	-	-	25	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 25ms.
10:32:45.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:32:46.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:33:30.91	---	-	-	-	-	*** SWS to 30 AFT
10:33:40.23	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 100ms.
10:33:42.63	SWS	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 25ms to 500ms.
10:33:45.10	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
10:33:47.75	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
10:33:49.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:33:57.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:34:35.59	---	-	-	-	-	*** SWS to 30 Fore
10:34:42.27	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 10ms.
10:34:48.39	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 50ms.
10:34:50.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:34:51.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:34:58.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:34:59.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:35:35.17	---	-	-	-	-	*** SWS to 20 AFT
10:35:43.65	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 250ms.
10:35:47.12	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
10:35:49.75	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 750ms.
10:35:52.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:36:00.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:36:47.20	---	-	-	-	-	*** SWS to 10 FORE
10:37:06.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:37:06.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:37:06.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:37:11.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:37:14.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:37:14.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:37:27.94	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws still at 20AFT
10:37:54.33	---	-	-	-	-	*** SWS to 10 FORE
10:38:00.77	SWS	-	-	25	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 25ms.
10:38:04.55	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 100ms.
10:38:07.37	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 25ms to 75ms.
10:38:09.76	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
10:38:11.69	SWS	-	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 350ms.
10:38:12.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:38:14.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:38:17.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:38:21.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:38:59.13	---	-	-	-	-	*** SWS to 10 AFT
10:39:02.30	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 150ms.
10:39:05.86	SWS	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 500ms.
10:39:07.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:39:13.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:39:50.05	---	-	-	-	-	*** SWS to 0 Degrees
10:39:59.91	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
10:40:01.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:40:07.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:42:02.95	---	-	-	-	-	*** SZA now 34.6 deg

10:42:22.04	---	-	-	-	*** Azimuth 75.06 deg
10:43:03.34	---	-	-	-	*** aircraft pitch angle on the ground is 0.66 deg nose up
10:43:43.15	---	-	-	-	*** all to idle in prep for start up, taxi and take off.
10:43:47.32	SWS	-	-	-	Idling
10:43:49.16	USH	-	-	-	Idling
10:43:50.83	LSH	-	-	-	Idling
10:51:41.03	---	-	-	-	*** next up an one the ground pirouette
10:52:06.77	---	-	-	-	*** SWS will be SZA +10 degrees for this
10:57:20.07	---	-	-	-	*** SZA is now 30.9
10:57:36.54	---	-	-	-	*** SWS to 40.9 approx for pirouette
10:57:53.24	---	-	-	-	*** 40.9 Fore
10:58:11.46	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:58:11.48	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:58:11.48	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:58:17.09	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:58:17.27	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:58:17.31	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:58:22.54	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:58:22.73	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:58:25.44	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:58:28.15	SWS	-	-	25	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 25ms.
10:58:31.25	SWS	-	-	150	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 150ms.
10:58:33.89	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:58:35.83	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:01:03.15	---	-	-	-	*** start heading on 045 mag
11:03:34.00	---	-	-	-	*** end pirouette
11:03:48.22	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 90 AFT for take off!
11:04:40.15	---	-	-	-	*** mistake...SWS was at 40.9 AFT during pirouette!!!
11:04:53.38	---	-	-	-	*** see above
11:04:58.95	---	-	-	-	*** see above
11:05:49.91	---	-	-	-	*** take off and start P1
11:06:15.06	---	-	-	-	*** s
11:06:15.16	SWS	174R	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
11:06:19.05	SWS	-	-	100	VIS int.time changed from 25ms to 100ms.
11:06:21.96	SWS	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 150ms to 300ms.
11:06:24.66	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:06:28.09	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:07:46.35	USH	-	-	50	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
11:07:48.97	USH	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 300ms.
11:07:51.81	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:07:55.25	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:11:20.02	SWS	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
11:11:21.91	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:11:24.35	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:11:49.89	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 171 Aft
11:24:06.12	---	-	-	-	*** end P1 start R1.1
11:24:11.78	LSH	-	-	400	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 400ms.
11:24:16.19	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:24:16.29	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:24:16.35	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:24:18.63	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:24:20.11	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:24:24.34	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:24:47.48	SWS	174R	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
11:26:38.55	---	-	-	-	*** at FL170
11:30:51.26	---	-	-	-	***
11:30:52.90	LSH	-	-	350	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 350ms.
11:30:56.84	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:31:04.78	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:36:34.19	---	-	-	-	*** end R1.1 start P2 descent
11:36:43.02	SWS	6F	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:36:49.49	SWS	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 300ms.
11:36:52.80	SWS	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 500ms.
11:36:55.89	SWS	-	-	150	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 150ms.
11:37:04.42	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 3 Fore
11:37:11.03	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

11:37:11.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:37:11.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:37:14.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:37:16.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:37:19.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:43:14.60	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 75ms.
11:43:18.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:23.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:45:10.56	SWS	-	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 350ms.
11:45:14.11	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
11:45:15.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:45:19.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:47:45.44	SWS	-	-	-	250	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 250ms.
11:47:47.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:47:50.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:53:57.49	---	-	-	-	-	*** end P2 start Run
11:54:08.32	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
11:54:15.83	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
11:54:19.28	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 150ms.
11:54:23.64	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 75ms.
11:54:30.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:54:30.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:54:30.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:54:32.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:54:33.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:54:38.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:54:46.99	LSH	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 250ms.
11:54:50.53	LSH	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
11:54:55.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:54:55.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:54:56.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:54:58.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:54:59.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:55:01.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:07:12.18	---	-	-	-	-	*** flying over combination desert surface
12:07:55.25	---	-	-	-	-	*** some sand, rocky outcrops
12:08:14.73	---	-	-	-	-	*** some shrub too
12:17:39.85	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:17:46.10	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 10ms.
12:17:48.78	SWS	-	-	-	75	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 75ms.
12:17:52.21	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
12:17:54.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:54.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:54.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:55.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:17:58.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:18:00.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:23:06.56	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
12:23:21.50	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
12:23:27.33	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 75ms.
12:23:30.21	SWS	-	-	-	150	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 150ms.
12:23:33.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:23:33.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:23:33.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:23:35.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:23:37.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:23:39.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:27:42.54	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:27:46.26	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 10ms.
12:27:49.14	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 150ms to 50ms.
12:27:56.50	SWS	-	-	-	25	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 25ms.
12:27:58.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:27:58.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:27:58.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:27:59.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:28:01.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:28:04.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:29:17.68	SWS	-	-	-	10	NIR int.time changed from 25ms to 10ms.
12:29:19.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

12:29:19.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:29:19.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:29:20.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:29:22.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:29:25.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:31:54.64	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
12:31:59.02	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 75ms.
12:32:04.00	SWS	-	-	-	150	NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 150ms.
12:32:07.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:32:08.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:36:18.46	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:36:21.68	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 10ms.
12:36:25.67	SWS	-	-	-	10	NIR int.time changed from 150ms to 10ms.
12:36:31.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:36:31.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:36:31.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:36:31.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:36:34.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:36:37.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:37:07.08	---	-	-	-	-	*** SZA 5.4 deg, azimuth 14.3
12:37:31.85	---	-	-	-	-	*** aircraft heading 088 deg at 2000ft asl
12:39:44.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws to azi +10 = 16F
12:39:53.53	SWS	-	-	-	250	NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 250ms.
12:39:57.70	SWS	-	-	-	150	NIR int.time changed from 250ms to 150ms.
12:40:02.09	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
12:40:04.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:40:06.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:40:37.17	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
12:40:41.49	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 50ms.
12:40:45.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:40:47.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:44:54.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws to 16F
12:44:58.82	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 10ms.
12:45:02.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:45:03.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:49:20.60	---	-	-	-	-	*** SWS to begin upward scanning run
12:49:42.75	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 point scan 50F to 50A
12:50:06.84	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws to 50 FORE
12:50:18.32	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 50ms.
12:50:22.72	SWS	-	-	-	250	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 250ms.
12:50:24.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:50:27.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:51:45.73	---	-	-	-	-	*** 50AFT
12:52:02.88	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 75ms.
12:52:06.76	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 250ms to 300ms.
12:52:10.97	SWS	-	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 350ms.
12:52:12.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:52:16.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:53:36.55	---	-	-	-	-	*** 40FORE
12:54:55.14	---	-	-	-	-	*** 40AFT
12:56:02.12	---	-	-	-	-	*** 30FORE
12:57:19.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** 30AFT
12:58:22.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** 20FORE
12:58:34.09	SWS	-	-	25	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 25ms.
12:58:38.43	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 200ms.
12:58:45.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:58:47.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:00:10.04	---	-	-	-	-	*** 20AFT
13:00:37.95	---	-	-	-	-	*** 10FARE
13:00:58.62	---	-	-	-	-	*** NOT YET 10FORE
13:01:26.88	---	-	-	-	-	*** 10 FORE NOW
13:01:33.88	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 25ms to 10ms.
13:01:36.73	SWS	-	-	-	75	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 75ms.
13:01:39.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:01:40.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:02:58.79	---	-	-	-	-	*** 10AFT
13:04:26.83	---	-	-	-	-	*** 0 DEGREES
13:04:30.95	SWS	-	-	-	25	NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 25ms.
13:04:35.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

13:04:35.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:04:35.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:04:36.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:04:39.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:04:41.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:06:20.26	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
13:08:49.91	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
13:08:57.56	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 50ms.
13:09:01.49	SWS	-	-	-	75	NIR int.time changed from 25ms to 75ms.
13:09:07.36	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 200ms.
13:09:12.17	SWS	-	-	-	150	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
13:09:15.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:09:15.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:09:15.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:09:17.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:09:19.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:09:21.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:28:29.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:28:29.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:28:29.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:28:31.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:28:32.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:28:34.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:46:33.76	---	-	-	-	-	*** END R2.1 START P3
13:55:13.23	LSH	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
13:55:16.14	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 400ms.
13:55:21.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:55:21.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:55:21.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:55:23.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:55:25.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:55:29.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:00:43.27	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
14:00:46.72	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 150ms to 300ms.
14:00:50.33	SWS	-	-	-	250	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
14:00:54.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:00:54.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:00:54.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:00:57.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:00:58.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:01:02.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:02:49.90	---	-	-	-	-	*** end p3 start r3.1 at FL190
14:03:00.42	LSH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 300ms.
14:03:07.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:03:07.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:03:07.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:03:10.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:03:11.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:03:15.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:11:55.08	---	-	-	-	-	*** in profile descent
14:19:11.86	---	-	-	-	-	*** end p4 start r4.1
14:19:21.60	---	-	-	-	-	*** at FL090
14:21:50.94	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 150ms.
14:21:57.33	USH	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 75ms.
14:22:00.18	USH	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 500ms.
14:22:04.90	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 400ms.
14:22:09.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:22:09.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:22:09.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:22:12.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:22:15.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:22:17.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:29:56.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:29:56.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:29:56.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:29:59.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:30:01.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:30:05.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:47:37.57	---	-	-	-	-	*** end R4.1 start P5

14:47:44.24	---	-	-	-	*** to FL190
14:55:16.09	---	-	-	-	*** approaching top of dust layer at FL165
14:58:07.22	---	-	-	-	*** end P5 and start R5.1 at FL190
15:07:55.61	---	-	-	-	*** end run 5.1 start P6
15:08:02.59	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:08:02.64	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:08:02.75	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:08:05.77	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:08:08.04	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:08:11.00	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:08:18.79	SWS	6F	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
15:08:29.62	---	-	-	-	*** sws to 3F for descent
15:08:34.93	SWS	-	-	300	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 300ms.
15:08:37.49	SWS	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 250ms to 500ms.
15:08:40.66	SWS	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
15:08:47.41	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:08:55.35	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:18:53.85	SWS	-	-	200	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
15:18:56.06	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:19:04.00	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:20:23.72	SWS	-	-	75	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 75ms.
15:20:26.05	SWS	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 400ms.
15:20:27.56	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:20:32.00	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:26:38.25	---	-	-	-	*** end P6 start R6.1 at 3000ft
15:27:53.22	SWS	174R	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
15:27:56.44	SWS	-	-	150	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 150ms.
15:27:59.47	SWS	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 300ms.
15:28:03.05	SWS	-	-	200	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 200ms.
15:28:07.14	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:28:07.20	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:28:07.55	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:28:10.57	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:28:12.83	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:28:15.52	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:28:18.22	---	-	-	-	*** cloud above
15:28:32.95	---	-	-	-	*** SLR at 3000ft near Niamey
15:33:05.98	USH	-	-	300	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 300ms.
15:33:09.51	USH	-	-	400	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 400ms.
15:33:13.96	USH	-	-	500	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
15:33:16.88	USH	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
15:33:20.26	LSH	-	-	750	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
15:33:23.50	USH	-	-	750	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
15:33:27.02	SWS	-	-	350	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 350ms.
15:33:30.00	SWS	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 750ms.
15:33:33.03	SWS	-	-	750	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 750ms.
15:33:39.18	USH	-	-	500	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
15:33:41.93	SWS	-	-	500	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
15:33:44.76	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:33:44.77	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:33:44.79	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:33:52.71	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:33:52.90	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:33:53.12	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:34:39.65	USH	-	-	350	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 350ms.
15:34:43.95	USH	-	-	250	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 250ms.
15:34:49.01	SWS	-	-	350	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 350ms.
15:34:53.23	SWS	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
15:34:55.31	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:34:55.53	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:34:55.56	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:35:00.76	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:35:03.46	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:35:03.66	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:43:11.69	---	-	-	-	*** end run start descent into Niamey
15:43:49.59	USH	-	-	100	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 100ms.
15:43:57.01	SWS	-	-	200	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 200ms.
15:43:59.85	SWS	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
15:44:03.51	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

15:44:03.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:44:03.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:44:07.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:44:11.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:44:11.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:45:07.68	---	-	-	-	-	*** on finals so Data stop and sws to 90AFT for landing

ARIES flight log

Flight: 13302

page 1 of 4

Date: 28 JUN 07 Operator(s): S. ROGERS

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: NOUAKCHOTT TO NIAMEY

AW 8
SR 5

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

5.1
0.6

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
10 03 15							
10 03 15	On the pan.	1x60	CH	C	71	42	Script 1 (1x60 CBB; 1x60 HBB)
10 05 17	"	"	CH	C	71	42	
10 06 50	"	480x1	Z	O	71	41	
10 10 55		1x60	CH	O	71	42	
10 27 40		1x60	CH	O	71	41	
10 29 02		480x1	Z	O	71	42	
10 33 05	- - -	1x60	CH	O			
10 34		480x1	Z	O			
10 38 34		1x60	CH	O	71	41	
10 39 52		480x1	Z	O	71	42	
10 43 57	- - -	1x60	CH	O	71	41	
10 44 55		480x1	Z	O	71	42	
10 50 12		1x60	CH	O	71	41	
10 51 29		360x1	Z	O	71	42	
10 54 32		1x60	CH	O	71	42	Power changeover.
10 55 56		240x1	Z	O	71	41	Taxiing
10 57 57		240x1	Z	O	71	42	
11 00 02		240x1	Z	O	71	42	Pirouette start at 11:00:53
11 02 03		240x0	Z	O	71	41	Aborted at end of pirouette.
11 03 37		1x60	CH	C			Take off.
	↑						
11 23 40	FL170?	1x60	CH	C	71	41	
11 24 56		480x1	N	C	71	41	Dusty below, surface visible. Clear above
11 28 58		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
11 30 15		240x1	N	C	71	41	
11 32 18		240x1	N	C	71	42	
11 34 20		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
11 35 45		240x1	N	C			Aborted at end of run.
11 36 40	↓	1x60	CH	C	71	41	

ARIES flight log

Flight: B302

page 2 of 4

Date:

Operator(s):

Res:

Gain A: B:

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
11 53 33	1800A	1x60	CH	C	71	41	
11 54 50	1800A 1800A	480x1	N	C	71	42	Bumpy.
11 58 56		1x60	CH	C			
12 00 15		480x1	N	C	71	41	
12 04 17		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
12 05 35		480x1	N	C	71	42	
12 09 45		1x60	CH	C	71	42	
12 10 58		480x1	N	C	71	41	
12 16 20		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
12 17 47		360x1	Z	O	71	41	
12 21 48		1x60	CH	C	71	42	
12 23 05		360x1	N	C	71	42	
12 26 05		1x60	CH	C	71	43	
12 27 26		240x1	Z	O	70	42	
12 30 23		1x60	CH	C	71	43	
12 31 42		360x1	N	C	71	43	
12 34 43		1x60	CH	C	71	43	
12 36 01		240x1	Z	O	71	43	
12 38 48		1x60	CH	C	71	44	
12 40 18		360x1	N	C	71	44	
12 43 14		1x60	CH	C	71	44	
12 44 28		240x1	Z	C	70	44	
12 47 29		1x60	CH	C	71	45	
12 48 56		360x1	N	C	71	45	
12 51 56		1x60	CH	C	71	45	
12 53 21		240x1	Z	O	71	44	Still low down, still bumpy.
12 55 32		240x1	N	C	71	46	
12 57 35		1x60	CH	C	71	46	→ Increasing MBS to 80°C to maintain separation.
12 59 32		1x60	CH	C	81	46	
13 00 48		240x1	Z	O	80	46	
13 02 56		240x1	N	C	81	46	

ARIES flight log

Flight: B302

page 3 of 4

Date:

Operator(s):

Res:

Gain A: B:

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
13 05 00	1800 ft agl	1x60	CH	C	81	46	"Unable to get instrument status" System restarted
13 13 17	1800 ft agl	1x60	CH	C	81	49	!
13 14 32		240x1	Z	O	81	49	
13 16 40		240x1	N	C	81	49	
13 18 46		1x60	CH	C	84	49	
13 20 00		240x1	Z	O	81	49	
13 22 10		240x1	N	C	81	50	
13 24 11		1x60	CH	C	81	50	
13 25 30		240x1	Z	O	81	50	
13 27 38		240x1	N	C	81	50	
13 29 38		1x60	CH	C	81	51	
13 31 00		240x1	Z	O	81	50	
13 33 11		240x1	N	C	81	51	
13 35 15		1x60	CH	C	81	51	
13 36 32		240x1	Z	O	81	51	
13 38 47		240x1	N	C	81	52	
13 40 49		1x60	CH	C	81	52	
13 41 42		240x1	Z	O	81	52	
13 43 49		240x1	N	C	81	52	
13 45 52	↑	1x60	CH	C	81	53	Cal in climb, Open slutter to help CBB Cool.
14 03 57	FL190	1x60	CH	C	81	45	↓
14 05 12		240x1	N	C	81	44	
14 07 13		1x60	CH	C	81	43	
14 08 37		240x1	N	C	81	42	Aborted at end of run.
14 09 02	↓	1x60	CH	C	81	41	
14 19 22	FL090	1x60	CH	C	81	41	
14 20 32		480x1	N	C	81	41	
14 24 32		1x60	CH	C	81	42	
14 25 48		480x1	N	C	81	41	
14 29		1x60	CH	C	81	41	

B302 flight manager

- ✓ NOW
- ✓ GIN
- ✓ CGPS
- ✓ INU
- ✓ DRS
- ✓ JW
- ✓ PSAP
- ✓ HEIMANN

Flight:

B302

KEY

- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- OK
- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nevezorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

Report Created 29/08/2007
08:44:21

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turb Centre-Static:
- Turb Left Right:
- Turb Up-Down:
- Turb Horizontal Chk:
- Turb Vertical Chk:
- Weather Radar:
- DLUs:**
- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:
- Aerosol**
- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3025 (AMS):
- INC:
- VACC:
- CPC 3010A (CVI):

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

02/07/2007 13:32:48

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B302

Date: 28 June 2007

Instruments

1. dry neph relative humidity suspect
2. nevz U/S
3. GIN data incorrect until rebooted about 13:40
4. de iced true temp isn't correct (JimH), possibly relates to true/dewpoint anomaly previously reported
5. ins velocity north; oscillations with 3 min period – example 1120 > 1150 (John Marsham)
6. Upper IR, signal and zero very noisy – data u/s for a period
7. ffssp overheat problem at low altitudes, possibly cabin interface. (Ok at height cool cabin)

Aircraft

Satcom-H Calls

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 28/06/07

Flight No: B302

Pre-Flighter: JT

Item	✓ or x	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
1	☒	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
<u>Aircraft Cabin</u>				
2	☒	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	CO2/Ar a little ↓ @ 2 bars.
3	☒	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	☒	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	☒	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	☒	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	☒	HORACE	Recording data	
8	☒	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	☒	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	☒	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	☒	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
12	☒	GPS	Checked	
13	☒	INU	Align	
14	☒	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	☒	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
16	☒	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
17	☒	FWVS	Set up	N/A
18	☒	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	☒	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	☒	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	☒	TWC	ON & Checked	NOT FIXED YET
22	☒	GE	Balance checked	
23	☒	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
24	☒	Hubs x 4	Checked ON	
25	☒	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	& CB on Port Fwd SSP
26	☒	CNC	Butanol filled	N/A.
27	☒	CGPS	Set up	SWITCHED ON - NOT LOGGING
28	☒	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
	☒	NO PH CALLS		ANDY WILSON TO PERFORM
	☐			
	☐			
External Checks overleaf				→

Pre-Flighter's Log

<u>Item</u>	<u>✓ or x</u>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
<u>External</u>				
29	☒	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	☒	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	☒	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	☒	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	☒	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	SHITTY & STRIPPED.
34	☒	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	☒	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	☒	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	☒	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	☒	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	NOT FITTED
39	☒	All other covers	Removed	
40	☐	Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
41	☐	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	☐	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				Signed
43	☒	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		
44	☒	ICEX applied		
45	☒	Traps empty (weekly only)		

Banizoumbou , N 13 32' 27" , E 02 39' 54" , Alt 250 m,
 PI : Didier Tarré , tanre@loa.univ-lille1.fr
 Level 1.0 AOT; Data from 27 JUN 2007

AOT_1020 : <0.857>
 AOT_870 : <0.869>
 AOT_675 : <0.884>
 AOT_440 : <0.903>

27 <- Day in GMT
 JUN
 2007

Version 2 DS

Dakar , N 14 23' 38" , W 16 57' 32" , Alt 0 m,
 PI : Didier Tarré , tanre@loa.univ-lille1.fr
 Level 1.0 AOT; Data from 27 JUN 2007

AOT_1020 : <1.172>
 AOT_870 : <1.145>
 AOT_675 : <1.150>
 AOT_440 : <1.114>

27 <- Day in GMT
 JUN
 2007

Version 2 DS

AOD T+36 (plotted 07z27/06/07)

At 12Z on 28/ 6/2007, from 00Z on 27/ 6/2007

Dust conc 20.000o merid xsect

At 12Z on 28/ 6/2007, from 00Z on 27/ 6/2007

Dust conc 17.500o merid xsect

At 12Z on 28/ 6/2007, from 00Z on 27/ 6/2007

Dust conc 15.000o merid xsect

At 12Z on 28/ 6/2007, from 00Z on 27/ 6/2007

Surface Dust concentration T+36 (plotted 07z27/06/07)

At 12Z on 28/ 6/2007, from 00Z on 27/ 6/2007

1e-5 1e-4 0.001 0.01 0.1 1

2000-5000ft Dust concentration T+36

1e-5 1e-4 0.001 0.01 0.1 1

At 12Z on 28/ 6/2007, from 00Z on 27/ 6/2007

0 4 8 12 16

Cloud Cover T+36 (plotted 07z27/06/07)

0 0.2 0.4 0.6 0.8 1

700hPa winds T+36

0 8 16 24 32

At 12Z on 28/ 6/2007, from 00Z on 27/ 6/2007

6hr Precip Accum T+30 to 36

0 0.2 0.4 0.6 0.8 1

0 1 5 20 50

B302 Images Emailed In Flight

EEA041 MSG dnat RGB 28 Jun 2007 0930 UTC

EEA041_20070628_0930.jpg

EEA041 MSG dnat RGB 28 Jun 2007 1015 UTC

EEA041_20070628_1015.jpg

EEA041 MSG dnat RGB 28 Jun 2007 1230 UTC

EEA041_20070628_1230.jpg

EEA041 MSG dnat RGB 28 Jun 2007 1345 UTC

EEA041_20070628_1345.jpg

61052 DRRN Niamey-Aero

	SLAT	13.47
	SLON	2.16
	SELV	227.0
	SHOW	-0.44
	LIFT	-4.84
	LFTV	-5.42
	SWET	182.0
	KINX	35.30
	CTOT	18.30
	VTOT	29.30
	TOTL	47.60
	CAPE	1305.
	CAPV	1439.
	CINS	-189.
	CINV	-132.
	EQLV	174.4
	EQTV	173.4
	LFCT	709.1
	LFCV	734.7
	BRCH	28.11
	BRCV	31.00
	LCLT	293.9
	LCLP	901.9
	MLTH	302.7
	MLMR	17.47
	THCK	5798.
	PWAT	50.54

12Z 28 Jun 2007

University of Wyoming

2007062812.61052.skewt.gif

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B302:

Log	Reason
De-brief	Sortie De-brief yet to be created by Jim Haywood
Cloud Physics Processing	Processing yet to be completed.
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page
Wet Nephelometer	No operator on GERBIL

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	19 Jan 2008	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

4 x Rearward Facing Cameras

4 x Up/Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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